

Impact Of Technological Advancements On Preservation And Innovation In The Field Of Music

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Abstract:

Today is the era of technology, where the entire human race is bowing before new inventions. While these new scientific discoveries and inventions have played a significant role in making human life happier and more enjoyable, they have also helped to expand the human mind and thinking. Be it the field of education or business, agriculture or industry, technology has influenced every field, which has not only increased productivity but also improved the quality and human lifestyle. If we talk about music, then, like other fields, ‘music’, which is synonymous with happiness, has also not remained untouched by the influence of technology. Technology has opened doors to new dimensions in the field of music, which has not only given rise to the trend of new electronic instruments but has also given rise to high-end inventions such as advanced equipments, high-quality tools for music production, high-end music software's, tools for video production, and tools related to music therapy, which have not only opened new doors of employment but have also played an important role in the preservation, innovation, social awareness, promotion, and conservation of music. Due to its far-reaching effects, not only musicians, teachers, students, researchers, but also the common man interested in music is benefiting. Therefore, the current study focuses on the contemporary study of the importance of technological advancements in the field of music, the aim of which is to present an analytical study of the impact of new inventions and technological discoveries on the preservation and innovation of music.

Keywords: Music, technological advancements, music and technology, musical hardware and software, electronic instruments.

Background

In this era, science commands admiration from all corners of the world for its remarkable inventions and advancements. Considering the new inventions of science, technology has gained a rapid pace in the world, whose far-reaching effects are not only making a significant contribution to the ease of human life, but also improving and making the daily life of the person easier in the form of various modern gadgets, devices, the internet, mechanization, etc. With the advancement of technology, manual labor has become obsolete in today's technologically advanced world. The modern era places greater value on smart work than industrious labor. Only technological advancement, which has impacted every aspect of human life, including education¹, daily living, healthcare², communication, art, culture³, entertainment, and transportation, has made this tradition of smart work possible. Throughout the modern era, technology has changed the structure of human life, and the biggest technological inventions of our time are the Internet and artificial intelligence. Today, the Internet and Artificial Intelligence dominate every field, whether it is transportation, communication, home appliances, factories, big machines in the industrial world, hospitals, schools, colleges, or universities. Today's smart gadgets, heavy engines, electricity, weapons, Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, vaccines, surgeries, astronomical discoveries, etc., are all the results of technological advances. In the absence of technology, imagining human life would be impossible. As technology has continuously advanced, while human life has gone through immense improvements, music, the most enjoyable form of entertainment, has also been

¹ Timotheou, S. et al. "Impacts of Digital Technologies on Education and Factors Influencing Schools' Digital Capacity and Transformation: A Literature Review." *Education and Information Technologies*, vol. 28, no. 6, 2023, pp. 6695-6726, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-022-11431-8>

² Alotaibi, Yasser K., and Frank Federico. "The Impact of Health Information Technology on Patient Safety." *Saudi Medical Journal*, vol. 38, no. 12, 2017, pp. 1173-1180, <https://doi.org/10.15537/smj.2017.12.20631>.

³ Kurt, Ibrahim & Gök, Hakan. Impact of Technology on the Perceptions of Culture Shock. *Mevlana International Journal of Moral and Values Education (MIJMVE)*, Vol. 2, 2015, pp. 21-28.

affected by technological advancements⁴. Due to the influence of technology, the music world has gone through a long journey through various changes, because of which not only opened the doors of new innovations, but preservation in music has also gained a new dimension with the help of various technological advancements⁵. Consequently, as technology has spread, human life has also become more advanced and happier, which has led to meaningful changes in all aspects of art and culture.

Usually, technology is the scientific and technological solution to the problems and difficulties associated with the daily lives of humans⁶. Under which new technology is invented in the form of innovation through the combined use of mechanization, scientific thinking, new ideas, and scientific principles, which not only signifies development but also plays an important role in improving human life and taking it to new dimensions⁷. When it comes to art, music has been the primary source of pleasure and entertainment since the dawn of time. It is the medium through which the combined disciplines of singing, playing instruments, and dancing are most perfectly united. History is witness to the fact that as man has progressed, all aspects of his life have been affected, of which music is also an important aspect. In this changing era of technology, music has also gone through various types of changes that are evident throughout history, including the ancient, medieval, modern, and present eras. From the study of the texts of the Vedic period, it is known that in this period, the folk instrument called '*Shatatantri or bana*' was very popular⁸; however, in later times, due to technological advancement, the instrument '*mat kokila*' became popular, which had

⁴ Kostek, Božena. "Music information retrieval—The impact of technology, crowdsourcing, big data, and the cloud in art." *Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, Vol-146, 2019, 2946-2946.

⁵ Lerch, Alexander. "The relation between music technology and the music industry." *Springer Handbook of Systematic Musicology*, 2018, pp. 899-909.

⁶ Salomon, Jean-Jacques. "What is technology? The issue of its origins and definitions *History and Technology*." Vol. 1, no. 2, 1984, pp. 113-156

⁷ Agar, Jon. "What is technology? *Annals of Science*". Vol. 77, no. 3, 2020, pp. 377-382, <https://doi.org/10.1080/00033790.2019.1672788>

⁸ Krishnaswami, S. "Musical instruments of India". Ministry of information and broadcasting-Government of India, pp. 21-25

fewer strings than the *bana*. In the modern era, the instrument called *Swarmandal* is an upgraded and modified version of this instrument. If we talk about percussion instruments, then in the texts of the Vedic period, there is mention of popular instruments called *dundubhi*, *bhoomi dundubhi*⁹, which later evolved to the form of *nagara*, *nagari* etc. after technological advancement. Human evolution progressed along with technology, and due to this evolution, many new chapters were written in the field of music. Consequently, numerous new instruments gained popularity, and various inventions were made to enhance the sound quality. Concepts of resonance, echo, and other phenomena were explored to increase the intensity of music, and palaces, auditoriums, and other places were built with sound quality in mind. Only with the development of modern technology were gut strings in instruments replaced with strings made of iron and other metals, which increased music's popularity and quality. In the medieval period, the use of many new instruments like the *tanpura*, *sitar*, *tabla*, *sarod*, *dilruba*, *rabab* etc. indicates that due to technological advancement of human civilization, music, the best means of entertainment, also kept going through new changes. In the modern era, technology changed the direction of human life, because of which technology started being used more often in music and many electronic instruments, such as electric guitar, Casio, electronic piano started being used. The inventions of the radio, television, gramophone, and microphone proved to be extremely advantageous for music as well.

Since technology has become more widely used in the present, many electronic instruments have come to be used on a wide scale in music, including electronic tabla, electronic tanpura, electric piano, casio, guitar, octopad, and electric violin. Technological advancement has led to much equipment like better-quality microphones, recording

⁹ Krishnaswami, S. "Musical instruments of India". Ministry of information and broadcasting-Government of India, pp. 21-25

equipment, puff filters, light and sound, etc., that have made music presentations more appealing (*Figure 1*).

Figure 1 Technological advancements in the field of music

New technologies have made it easier to prove the effectiveness of music therapy¹⁰. In the present time, it is almost impossible to imagine how life would be without artificial

¹⁰ Barbara J. Crowe, Robin Rio. "Implications of Technology in Music Therapy Practice and Research for Music Therapy Education: A Review of Literature". *Journal of Music Therapy*, Vol. 41, no. 4, 2004, pp. 282–320, <https://doi.org/10.1093/jmt/41.4.282>.

intelligence and the internet. In such a situation, Artificial Intelligence and the Internet have opened new doors of possibilities in the music world through Facebook, Instagram, YouTube, as well as numerous automated music production software, websites, apps, etc. Apart from this, tools related to audio and video production, online platforms, e-seminars, webinars, learning from the internet, huge music databases, data storage devices and many more are the result of technological advancement only, due to which the scope of the music world today has expanded a lot. Thus, it can be effectively said that the use of technology in modernity has proved to be a milestone for music which not only helped in innovation in music but also played an important role in the preservation of music.

Significance of the study

New technological advancements in science have the power to impact every facet of human existence, including social, political, economic, and familial spheres, as well as the arts and cultures. In such circumstances, if technology is appropriately utilized in the field of music, then undoubtedly better outcomes will emerge, which will benefit not only music enthusiasts but also artists, students, researchers, etc. Keeping this in mind, the current research work presents a study of those factors related to music and technology that facilitate innovation and preservation in the field of music.

Objective

The objective of the study is to investigate the Impact of technological advancements on preservation and innovation in the field of music.

Materials and methods

The nature of this study is qualitative. The primary data gathered from depth interviews, introspection and secondary data gathered from various books, journals, articles, and an analytical study is presented.

Impact of technological advancements in the field of music

In the modern era, technology is rapidly affecting every aspect of human existence. The use of technology has brought about many changes in the field of music. Technology has not only influenced the way that music is taught, but it has also altered how people think about and feel about music. Whereas in ancient times, music was considered only a thing of entertainment, it is now recognized as a vital component that plays a significant role in human mental, physical, and social development. In olden times, where music education was limited only to a *few gharanas*, the spread of technology has played an important role in making music accessible to the common man by taking it to every home.

Aside from this, while music was previously confined to the royal families, today music is reaching out to the common people and playing a significant role in their lives. Today, music has not only benefited artists, but has also created a huge industry that has provided many people with golden employment opportunities. Today, music has become more than just art; it has become a big business idea that has dramatically changed people's lifestyles. As technology has spread, Indian music is now easily heard, understood, learned, and followed in foreign countries and foreign music in India. Therefore, the spread of technology has greatly contributed to the evolution of music. Despite the use of technology, music has been limited to the *mujra* of old royal houses, even today. However, the use of technology has also negatively impacted the quality of music. The use of software or hardware such as autotune, recording software, live plugins, mixing, etc., makes it easy to

make a dissonant sound melodious, make a slow sound louder, change pitch, base, treble, etc. As a result, today no artist exists to compete with the great artists such as *Ghulam Ali*, *Salamat Ali*, *Nazakat Ali*, *Pandit Ravi Shankar*. It is important to note, however, that technology has also had positive effects on the field of music, since it has enabled not only the development of new innovations every day but also the preservation, promotion, and propagation of music at a higher level.

Innovation through technological advancements in music

Music is a field where there is a lot of scope for innovation. Western scholars like *Crochet*, *Aristotle*, *Plato*, *Hegel*, *Baumgarten* and Indian scholars like *Kalidasa* and *Nagarjuna* have stressed the importance of innovation by linking art with beauty.

Figure 2 Technology-induced modifications in the field of music, that encouraged creative innovation.

When any art is innovated and changed according to the times, it becomes beautiful. In addition to providing mental peace, this process of innovation doubles its impact in the field of music, leaving a lasting impression on listeners¹¹. Innovation in music is not only related to the attachment and expression of musical notes but is related to every such experiment which makes musical activities more melodious with its style, quality, structure

¹¹ Regner, Tobias. "Innovation of music." *The Economics of Copyright*. Edward Elgar Publishing, 2003. pp. 104-117.

and gives immense pleasure to listeners. Music has achieved new dimensions of innovation due to technological advancement (figure 2).

As technology advanced, new equipment and mechanical changes came into vogue to make human life easier and happier. Thus, artists could create a controlled environment for music practice, and new innovations in the field of music could be supported as a result. A variety of new discoveries in the field of music, including better equipment, software, hardware, electronic instruments, musical tools, radio, television, the internet, artificial intelligence, and more, played a major part in expanding its scope and spreading it throughout the world. Because of this, music began to be understood by all facets of society, including elite musicians, students, teachers, music enthusiasts, and researchers. As a result, music began to be associated with other academic disciplines such as psychology, physiology, yoga, and society and new avenues for innovation became available.

New platforms for music learning have been developed, which has resulted in new possibilities for music innovation. By using e-seminars, webinars, and e-concerts, participants from across the country and abroad are now participating in discussions and discussing music-related problems, inspiring innovation in music as a result. After the technological advancements in musical equipment, sound is recorded and presented better, so that everyone can express his imagination through music, which is a sign of musical innovation. The immense development of technology today has not only provided a better platform for music lovers through various online platforms like Facebook, YouTube, and Instagram but has also played an important role in improving their economic condition through music. Technology breakthroughs have made it possible to use music therapy effectively. Therefore, it can be stated that, because of technological growth, music has undergone endless changes that have both doubled the rate of musical innovation and improved its quality.

Preservation through technological advancements in music

Music art is such an art which is very important to preserve. To preserve any kind of art or object, it is necessary to keep it safe. For example, if a painting is to be preserved, then we must store it carefully in a moisture-free and dry place using high-quality paper, pencils, colors, etc. But this is not feasible with music since it is an audio art. In ancient times, any musical composition could be preserved only by memorizing it and writing it down through *swarlipi tradition*; these practices continued through the *Guru-Shishya parampara*. But history is witnessing that, due to various reasons, neither of these approaches was at all adequate to preserve musical compositions. Since music is an audio art, thus, to preserve the musical compositions, a huge database, storage devices, better quality recording equipment, etc. were required, the lack of which has been fulfilled only due to technological advancements.

The advancement of humankind resulted in the inventions of a variety of storage devices, including hard drives, pen drives, cassettes, CDs, online storage databases, and others, which played an important role in preserving historical musical compositions and trends for upcoming generations. We are living in an era of digitalization. In such a scenario, it is the result of technological advancement that every musical composition is available online on the internet. Technological advancement is not limited only to the preservation of musical compositions, singing style, various genres, musical events and so on, but has also had various far-reaching effects on art and culture (Figure 3).

Only after technological advancement has it become possible to organize various massive musical events, and concerts, in which millions of people from across the nation and overseas take part. These concerts encourage musical innovation and preservation in addition to spreading culture.

Figure 3 Technology-induced changes in the field of music, that contribute significantly in music preservation.

With the development of technology, many websites, e-resources, and musical databases have gained popularity and contributed significantly to the preservation of music. Modern equipment with advanced technology has made it easier to record and process high-quality music, leading to significant advancements in the field of recording and reproduction and making it simpler to preserve contemporary music for future generations. In this era of digitalization, the trend of e-conferences, e-webinars, e-concerts and so on gained a lot of traction, which allows a person to present in any country while seated anywhere in the world.

This is a significant change from the perspective of preservation in the field of music. Using various online platforms, the internet and digitalization trends have given artists, experts, students, and teachers of music a new platform. which enables teachers to teach their students, allows students to take lessons from multiple professionals, and allows artists to share their creations with the public. Through audio - video production, it has become easy to preserve and enhance any musical composition, which we can use for a long time for various purposes like educational or social awareness purpose, etc. Thus, it is possible to state

that, the changes brought about in the music world due to technological advancement are no less than a miracle which has played a significant role in the preservation of music.

Conclusion

Thus, it can be said that music, which symbolizes joy, has gone through numerous transformations because of the endless advancement of technology. These transformations to music have not only changed its medium, but technological advancements have also given music new dimensions through a variety of discoveries and inventions. Due to that music, combined with subjects like medicine, yoga, literature, science, mathematics, physiology, psychology etc., has emerged as a miraculous factor in various discoveries related to human welfare. Apart from this, with the spread of technology, not only the dimensions related to music teaching and music learning have got a new direction in the form of various e-platforms, but various technological inventions have also led to the promotion of new gadgets, software, hardware. These modern changes in music have not only improved the quality of music but have also opened new avenues of innovation and preservation. Thus, it can be effectively said that technological advancements have played a significant role in expanding the possibilities for musical innovation and preservation.

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